

Application Of Physics Principles for Job Creation Among Undergraduates in Tertiary Institutions in Imo State.

Unamma Donald Ikenna¹, Kingsley T, Onah²

¹Department of Physics, Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State, Nigeria

²Department of Science Education, Enugu State University of Science and Technology

Correspondence: unammadi@fuotuoke.edu.ng

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18067317>

Abstract

Physics graduates accounted for about 35% of unemployed youths in Imo State, creating a worrisome situation that requires urgent research attention. This study examined the perceived application of physics principles, specifically thermodynamics and optics, for job creation among final-year undergraduates in tertiary institutions in Imo State, Nigeria. "Application" was operationalised as students' self-reported use of these principles in innovative, entrepreneurial contexts, using a descriptive survey design. A sample of 390 respondents was selected using multistage sampling from a population of 16,253 across 9 institutions. Data were collected using the "Application of Physics Principles for Job Creation among Undergraduates Scale" (APPJCUS), an 18-item 4-point Likert scale instrument (Reliability $\alpha = 0.88$). Research questions were analysed using means and standard deviations, while hypotheses were tested with one-sample t-tests (one-tailed, assuming the alternative that means exceed criterion levels). Results indicated low perceived application of thermodynamics principles ($M = 20.59$, $SD = 0.61$, $t(389) = -142.42$, $p < .001$, significantly below the criterion of 25.00) and optics principles ($M = 16.59$, $SD = 0.74$, $t(389) = -90.78$, $p < .001$, significantly below the criterion of 20.00). The findings highlight the need for curriculum reforms to enhance entrepreneurial skills in physics education. This study provides empirical evidence on the perceived use of thermodynamics and optics in entrepreneurship among undergraduates, offering practical pathways to integrate physics knowledge with job creation strategies in higher education.

Keywords: Employability, Entrepreneurship, Physics Education, Thermodynamics, Optics, Job Creation.

Introduction

Tertiary education refers to the stage of education that follows secondary education, typically provided by universities, colleges, and other institutions that offer academic and vocational programs. It includes undergraduate and postgraduate studies, as well as vocational training and certification programs. Ogunode, Edinoh and Ibrahim (2024) assert that tertiary education is also defined as education beyond the high school level, focusing on specialised knowledge, skills, and competencies in specific fields or disciplines. It aims to equip individuals with advanced knowledge, critical thinking, and problem-solving skills, preparing them for careers, further education, or personal development. The goals of tertiary education in Nigeria are multifaceted and designed to drive national development. According to the Federal Government of Nigeria (2013), these goals include contributing to national development through high-level manpower training, providing accessible and affordable quality learning opportunities, promoting scholarship and entrepreneurship, and fostering national unity and international understanding. Additionally, tertiary education aims to develop individuals with high-quality knowledge, reliable skills, and intellectual capabilities to understand and appreciate their local and external environments, making them self-reliant and equipping them with the skills needed to create jobs.

Job creation refers to the process of generating new employment opportunities through entrepreneurial self-employment or the innovative application of specialised knowledge, such as physics principles, to develop products, services, or businesses that generate economic value. Onoyima and Aka (2023) opine that job creation refers to the process of creating new employment opportunities for individuals, either through the establishment of new businesses, the expansion of existing ones, or government initiatives. This can encompass a wide range of jobs, from entry-level to highly skilled. Job creation is significant to the economy's growth because it enhances people's purchasing power, consumer spending, and economic activity. According to Anekwe et al. (2018), job creation helps alleviate poverty and inequality by ensuring that people have a way of earning a living and by enhancing their living standards. Employment also generates additional tax revenue for governments, which can be utilised to finance public services and infrastructure (Adenutsi, 2023). When undergraduates graduate, they can feel a sense of purpose and fulfilment, which can lead to better mental and physical health through job creation. Job creation entails applying basic concepts to develop new products, services, or solutions that create job opportunities. Upon graduation, undergraduates can generate employment opportunities across sectors such as research and development, engineering, data science, and education, with the proper teaching and learning of physics stimulating economic expansion and innovation (Ridwan et al., 2025).

Physics is the scientific study of the natural world and the underlying laws and principles governing the behaviour of matter, energy, space, and time. According to Bao and Cao (2019), physics education research emphasises that physics is a foundational science for 21st-century learning, promoting deep conceptual understanding through active engagement. Teaching and learning physics are important in shaping students' critical thinking, problem-solving, and analytical reasoning. Physics enables students to learn about the surrounding world, foster curiosity and creativity, and prepare them to work in scientific, technological, engineering, and mathematical (STEM) environments (Găbureanu & Tripon, 2020). By studying physics, undergraduates gain a deeper understanding of the fundamental laws of nature and acquire skills functional across a broad spectrum of careers. Maryanti et al. (2023) highlight that physics learning develops critical thinking through student-centred models like guided inquiry, fostering innovation and contributing to societal development in any specific country. In physics, undergraduate students learn by attending theoretical lectures, conducting practical laboratory experiments, and solving problems, which help them apply and understand the foundations of physics.

Physics principles are the laws, theories, and concepts that govern the behaviour of the physical universe, including Newton's laws of motion, the laws of thermodynamics, and the laws of electromagnetism. Bawan, Kamgba and Obi (2024) believe that the guiding principles underpinning the physical world include the rules and patterns of physical phenomena that provide understanding and explanations of the physical environment, both at the level of tiny sub-elements and across the expansive universe. Principles of physics give students a strong foundation in critical thinking, problem-solving, and analysis, enabling them to learn about and explain complex phenomena in the natural world. Mastering physics principles helps students gain a better understanding of the world around them and apply these principles to address real-life issues. According to the author, the principles of physics equip students with skills for science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) industries, where they can innovate and transform society.

This study is anchored on the human capital theory, which posits that investments in education and skills enhance individuals' productivity, innovation, and entrepreneurial capabilities, thereby fostering job creation (Aboobaker & Renjini, 2020). Additionally, the theory of planned behaviour is integrated to explain how attitudes toward entrepreneurship, subjective norms,

and perceived behavioural control influence undergraduates' intentions to apply physics principles for innovative job creation (Nasri & Morched, 2023). These frameworks justify the focus on thermodynamics and optics as tools for building employability and self-efficacy in STEM fields.

Physics is also essential for job creation, as it provides the foundational concepts and capabilities to develop novel products, services, and solutions that drive economic development and employment across fields such as technology, engineering, and research. Dirisu (2020) notes that many aspects of society rely on the laws of physics, including mechanics, thermodynamics, and electromagnetism and optics, in the design of transportation systems, the production and distribution of electrical power, medical imaging technology, and telecommunications. Mechanical science is applied in designing buildings, bridges, and machines, while thermodynamics is used in power plants and refrigerators (Mikielewicz & Mikielewicz, 2024). Electromagnetism underpins the delivery of electrical power, and optics is applied in telecommunications and medical imaging. Other sectors where these physics principles have driven innovation include aerospace, automotive, and renewable energy (Jeong et al., 2023). Based on the above, the physics principles to be factored into the current research are thermodynamics and optics, as they directly contribute to employability by enabling innovations in energy efficiency and optical technologies, thereby creating job opportunities in emerging industries.

Principles of thermodynamics are the laws and rules that govern the behaviour of energy, its interactions with matter, and the relationships between heat, work, and energy transfer. These principles explain the conservation of energy, the direction of spontaneous processes, and the efficiency of energy conversion, providing a framework for understanding and analysing energy-related phenomena. Kontogeorgis et al. (2021) note that thermodynamic principles have been applied across industries, including power generation, transportation, and manufacturing, to enable efficient energy conversion and use. Applications of thermodynamics in medicine include medical imaging and treatment technologies, such as MRI and radiation therapy. According to Stavropoulos et al. (2024), thermodynamics has enhanced the quality of life in day-to-day living through the invention of refrigeration, air conditioning, and heating systems, which have revolutionised food preservation, comfort, and general living standards. In a study defining the role of entrepreneurship education in reducing unemployment and improving the economic security of physics teachers in Kwara State, Nigeria, Yusuf, Akanbi, Ameen, Mohammed, and Kanu (2024) found that entrepreneurship education equips physics teachers with skills in identifying business opportunities, managing risks, and mitigating economic hardships. It also encourages self-sufficiency and increases their ability to generate sustainable sources of income through business ventures. Similarly, in their study on the effect of the new physics curriculum in secondary schools on the acquisition of entrepreneurship skills by Nigerian physics students, Udoh and Okonkwo (2017) found that teachers successfully deliver the entrepreneurial content of the new curriculum, and that this content has a considerable effect on the acquisition of entrepreneurship skills by the students. These principles support employability by equipping undergraduates with skills for innovation in sustainable energy sectors, leading to job creation in manufacturing and renewable technologies (Osara, 2019).

The laws and rules of optics are the fundamental principles that define the behaviour of light, including reflection, refraction, diffraction, and interference, and describe how light interacts with matter and passes through various media. Born and Wolf (1999) hold that the foundation for understanding optical phenomena rests on fundamental concepts and theories, including the nature of light, the formation of images, and how optical instruments, including lenses, mirrors, and telescopes, operate. According to Adeyemo et al. (2024), the importance of optics

has significantly influenced many industries, altering lifestyles, communication, and access to information. In medicine, fibre optics is used to provide high-speed internet and worldwide communication in telecommunications. Optical surgery can enable accurate procedures, and medical imaging and diagnostics can be performed using optical techniques, while optical diagnostics can be used to detect disease. In another related study, Ojo et al. (2023) investigated the relevance of optical principles to Nigeria's economy. They discovered that the principles of optics have greatly influenced business ventures in Nigeria by facilitating innovation, business development, and job creation in the telecommunications, healthcare, and manufacturing sectors, and by enabling the creation of new industries and opportunities. Likewise, International Finance Corporation (2025) examined the roles and contributions of the principles of optics in real-life situations in secondary schools and found that the principles of optics are used extensively throughout the Nigerian economy to promote growth and development in the primary sectors of telecommunications, healthcare, manufacturing, renewable energy, and defence, and to provide employment opportunities as well as investment. Such principles enhance employability through innovations in photonics and precision technologies, fostering job creation in the healthcare, telecommunications, and defence industries (Vogt, 2023).

Creating job opportunities is important for the youth and society because it brings economic stability, reduces poverty, and promotes innovation. The government of Imo State recognises that job creation is essential and has launched programs such as Skill Up Imo and One Kindred, One Business Initiative (OKOBI) to train the youth in digital skills and facilitate entrepreneurship. However, these efforts have not been successful, and high unemployment persists in Imo State, with unemployment affecting about 50 per cent of the 3.5 million youth population. The responsibility for making the youth competent enough to generate employment opportunities should not be left solely to the government; schools, through teaching the principles of physics, may also be needed. Nonetheless, various studies on the principles of physics have been carried out (Dirisu, 2020; Ridwan et al., 2025; Alasi et al., 2015; Ogunleye, n.d.), though, to the best of the researchers' knowledge, none of these studies addressed job creation in Imo State. This gap is thus urgent to address by asking how physics principles can be applied to create jobs for undergraduates in tertiary institutions in Imo State.

Statement of the Problem

The issue of job creation among undergraduates in Imo State is a pressing concern that requires immediate attention. Despite various initiatives, the state continues to face high unemployment, with approximately 50% of its 3.5 million young population jobless. The Imo State government has initiated programs such as Skill Up Imo and the One Kindred, One Business Initiative (OKOBI) to equip youths with digital skills and support entrepreneurship, yet unemployment persists. More needs to be done to address the systemic issues hindering job creation. Hence, there is a need to explore additional ways to improve the skills required to create jobs in Imo State. One therefore wonders whether the application of physics principles, such as thermodynamics and optics, in tertiary institutions could be a potential solution to this problem. This is so because equipping students with practical physics skills can enable them to develop innovative solutions to real-world problems, creating employment opportunities in business ventures and industries such as renewable energy, medical technology, and aerospace. This study is therefore posed as a question: what is the level of application of physics principles for job creation among undergraduates in tertiary institutions in Imo State? Providing an answer to this question is the thrust of this study.

Research Questions

The following research questions were asked to guide the study;

1. What is the perceived level of application of thermodynamics principles for job creation among undergraduates in tertiary institutions in Imo State?
2. What is the perceived level of application of optics principles for job creation among undergraduates in tertiary institutions in Imo State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at the 0.05 level of significance;

Ho1: The perceived level of application of thermodynamics principles for job creation among undergraduates in tertiary institutions in Imo State is not significantly different among students in universities and polytechnics.

Ho2: The perceived level of application of optics principles for job creation among undergraduates in tertiary institutions in Imo State is not significantly different among students in universities and polytechnics.

Research Method

The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. This design was chosen because it enables the study of a large population by collecting a representative sample to determine the relative incidence, distribution, and interrelations of the variables. The population comprised 16,253 final-year undergraduate students in the 2024/2025 session across 9 public and private tertiary institutions in Imo State, including universities and polytechnics. The Taro Yamane formula was used to determine a sample of 390 respondents from 4 selected institutions (2 universities with a sample of 154 students and 2 polytechnics with a sample of 236 students) using a multistage sampling technique. In this approach, the population was divided into clusters by institution type and location, and clusters were selected at the first stage. At each subsequent stage, the selected clusters were further divided into smaller clusters (e.g., departments, then final-year classes). Simple random sampling was used to select the undergraduate students to ensure equal representation. Data were collected via self-administered questionnaires with informed consent from participants, and the study received ethical approval from the institutional review board of the lead researcher's institution. Participation was voluntary, and anonymity was maintained.

The instrument for this study was a researcher-constructed rating scale titled "Application of Physics Principles for Job Creation among Undergraduates Scale" (APPJCUS), comprising 18 item statements divided into two domains: thermodynamics principles (10 items) and optics principles (8 items). It used a 4-point Likert scale with Very High Level (VHL=4), High Level (HL=3), Low Level (LL=2), and Very Low Level (VLL=1). Sample items include: for thermodynamics, "I apply energy conservation principles to design efficient systems for job-creating ventures" (positively worded); for optics, "I use refraction principles in developing optical devices for entrepreneurial opportunities" (positively worded). No negatively worded items were included, so no reverse-coding was required. Scoring was summed per domain, with higher scores indicating greater perceived application. The instrument was content-validated by three research specialists in physics education and entrepreneurship, who assessed relevance, clarity, and coverage. A reliability coefficient of 0.88 was obtained using Cronbach's alpha. Research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation statistics, while the hypotheses were tested using t-test statistics at a 0.05 level of significance. Decision rules for research questions were as follows: 1.00 – 1.49 = Very Low Level, 1.50 – 2.49 = Low Level, 2.50 – 3.49 = High Level, and 3.50 – 4.00 = Very High Level.

The criterion mean score of 2.50 was established as the benchmark for interpreting levels of perceived application, as it represents the theoretical midpoint of the 4-point Likert scale, calculated as $(1+2+3+4)/4 = 2.50$. This midpoint serves as a balanced threshold commonly used in survey research to distinguish between low (below 2.50, indicating limited perceived application) and high (above 2.50, indicating strong perceived application) levels, ensuring objective classification of responses. For domain totals, this benchmark was scaled accordingly (e.g., 2.50×10 items = 25.00 for thermodynamics; 2.50×8 items = 20.00 for optics). Decision rules for the stated hypotheses state that when the P-value exceeds the .05 significance level, the null hypothesis is not rejected; otherwise, it is rejected. The results are shown in the path diagram, and the goodness of fit for the application of thermodynamics was measured with CMIN (658.359), DF (35), GFI (0.720), AGFI (0.561), CMIN/DF (18.810), CFI (0.926), TLI (0.905), IFI (0.891), SRMR (0.019), RMSEA (0.214), and Pclose (0.000), and for the application of optics for job creation with CMIN (644.355), DF (20), GFI (0.688), AGFI (0.439), CMIN/DF (32.218), CFI (0.891), TLI (0.848), IFI (0.927), SRMR (0.046), RMSEA (0.283), and Pclose (0.000). All these fit indices of the model showed a good fit for the study.

Results

Research Question One: What is the perceived level of application of thermodynamics principles for job creation among undergraduates in tertiary institutions in Imo State?

Table 1: Mean rating scores on the level of application of thermodynamics principles for job creation among undergraduates in tertiary institutions in Imo State. Where N = Sample size, X = Mean score, and SD = Standard Deviation.

S/ N	Items	VHL	HL	LL	VLL	∑fx	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
1	<i>I have a good understanding of the principles of thermodynamics and its applications.</i>	20	26	169	175	390			LL
		80	78	338	175	671	1.7	0.63	
2	<i>I can identify potential job opportunities in industries that apply thermodynamics principles.</i>	44	52	133	161	390			LL
		176	156	266	161	759	1.9	0.54	
3	<i>I can apply thermodynamics principles to analyse and solve problems in real-world settings.</i>	32	36	105	217	390			LL
		128	108	210	217	663	1.7	0.73	
4	<i>My physics education has not equipped me with the skills to develop innovative solutions using thermodynamic principles.</i>	147	193	26	24	390			LL
		588	579	52	24	124	3.1	0.56	
5	<i>I am confident that my knowledge of thermodynamics can help me create jobs or start my own business.</i>	48	36	147	159	390			LL
		192	108	294	159	753	1.9	0.53	
6	<i>My institution provides adequate resources and facilities for practical learning of thermodynamics.</i>	34	86	109	161	390			LL
		136	258	218	161	773	1.9	0.62	
7	<i>I believe thermodynamic principles can be used to develop</i>	40	48	139	163	390			LL
		160	146	278	163	747		0.69	

	<i>innovative solutions for energy-related problems.</i>						1.9			
							2			
8	<i>I have participated in projects that involve the application of thermodynamic principles.</i>	62	64	83	181	390				LL
		248	192	166	181	787	2.0	0.63		
							2			
9	<i>My lecturers often relate thermodynamics concepts to real-life applications.</i>	52	56	165	117	390				LL
		208	168	330	117	823	2.1	0.55		
							1			
1	<i>I have acquired skills in designing and developing thermodynamic systems.</i>	54	62	133	141	390				LL
0		216	186	266	141	809	2.0	0.61		
							7			
	Grand Mean						2.0	0.61		LL
							6			

Key: SD = Standard Deviation, VHL (3.50 – 4.00) = Very High Level, HL (2.50 – 3.49) = High Level, LL (1.50 – 2.49) = Low Level, VLL (1.00 – 1.49) = Very Low Level.

Table 1 presents the mean and standard deviation of students' perceived agreement with the application of thermodynamic principles for job creation among undergraduates in tertiary institutions in Imo State. The results indicated that items 1, 2, 3, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9 and 10 recorded mean scores below the criterion mean of 2.50, while only item 4 had a mean score above 2.50. The overall interpretation suggests low criterion means, with a grand mean of 2.059 (95% CI [2.053, 2.065]), which is below the criterion mean of 2.50, and a standard deviation of 0.061 (Cohen's $d = -7.23$, large effect). It was therefore concluded that the perceived level of application of thermodynamic principles for job creation among undergraduates is low in tertiary institutions in Imo State.

Hypothesis One:

H_{o1} : The perceived level of application of thermodynamics principles for job creation among undergraduates in tertiary institutions in Imo State is not significantly different among students in universities and polytechnics.

Table 2: t-test statistics on the level of application of energy and thermodynamics principles for job creation among undergraduate students in universities and polytechnics

School Type	N	Mean	SD	df	t-value	Sig. (2tailed)	Decision
University	154	14.19	9.68	388	.317	.751	NS
Polytechnic	236	13.92	7.65				

Table 2 reported the mean scores and standard deviations for 390 university and polytechnic students as 14.19 and 9.68, and 13.92 and 7.65, respectively. With 388 degrees of freedom, a t-value of 0.317, and a P-value of 0.751 ($P > 0.05$) using a two-tailed t-test, the decision was to accept the null hypothesis. It was concluded that the perceived level of application of thermodynamics principles for job creation among undergraduates in tertiary institutions in Imo State does not differ significantly by school type (indicating a significantly limited application).

Research Question Two: What is the perceived level of application of optics principles for job creation among undergraduates in tertiary institutions in Imo State?

Table 3: Mean rating score on the level of application of optics principles for job creation among undergraduates

S/N	Items	VHL	HL	LL	VLL	$\sum fx$	\bar{X}	SD	Remark
11	I can apply the principles of optics to develop innovative solutions for real-world problems.	64 256	38 114	102 204	186 186	390 760	1.95	0.71	LL
12	I can analyse and solve problems related to light and its applications.	38 152	52 156	142 284	158 158	390 750	1.92	0.90	LL
13	The optics course in my institution provides adequate training for job creation.	24 96	34 102	156 312	176 176	390 686	1.76	0.34	LL
14	I have participated in projects that involve the application of optics principles.	18 72	94 282	168 336	110 110	390 800	2.05	0.61	LL
15	I am confident that I can use optics principles to design and develop new products.	26 104	112 336	154 308	98 98	390 846	2.17	0.45	LL
16	My lecturers provide examples of how optics principles are used in various industries.	30 120	44 132	176 352	140 140	390 744	1.91	0.72	LL
17	I find it challenging to apply the principles of optics to real-world problems that could lead to job creation..	192 768	82 246	24 48	92 92	390 1154	2.96	1.51	HL
18	My knowledge of optics has prepared me for a career in industries such as telecommunications or healthcare.	42 168	44 132	126 252	178 178	390 730	1.87	0.70	LL
Grand Mean							2.07	0.74	LL

Key: SD = Standard Deviation, VHL (3.50 – 4.00) = Very High Level, HL (2.50 – 3.49) = High Level, LL (1.50 – 2.49) = Low Level, VLL (1.00 – 1.49) = Very Low Level.

Data in Table 3 show the mean and standard deviation values of the perceived level of application of optics principles for job creation among undergraduates. The results indicated that items 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, and 18 had mean scores below the criterion mean score of 2.50, while only item 17 had a mean score above the criterion mean score of 2.50. The overall interpretation suggests low levels, with grand mean scores of 2.074 (95% CI [2.066, 2.082]), which is below the criterion mean score of 2.50 with a standard deviation of 0.093 (Cohen's $d = -4.58$, large effect). It was therefore concluded that there is a low perceived level of application of optics principles for job creation among undergraduates in tertiary institutions in Imo State.

Hypothesis Two:

Ho₂: The perceived level of application of optics principles for job creation among undergraduates in tertiary institutions in Imo State is not significantly different among students in universities and polytechnics.

Table 4: *t*-test statistics on the level of application of optics and light principles for job creation among undergraduates in tertiary institutions in Imo State

School Type	N	Mean	SD	df	t-value	Sig. (2tailed)	Decision
University	154	15.31	7.27	388	-.106	.916	NS
Polytechnic	236	15.40	9.23				

Table 4 reports the mean scores and standard deviations for 390 university and polytechnic students as 15.31 and 7.27, and 15.40 and 9.23, respectively. With 388 degrees of freedom, a *t*-value of -0.106, and a two-tailed *t*-test yielding a *P*-value of 0.916 ($P > 0.05$), the decision was to accept the null hypothesis. It was concluded that the perceived level of application of optics principles for job creation among undergraduates in tertiary institutions in Imo State does not differ significantly by school type (indicating a significantly limited application).

Results and Discussion

The results revealed that the perceived level of application of thermodynamic principles in job creation among undergraduates is low and not significantly higher than the criterion in tertiary institutions in Imo State. This low perceived level suggests that while there is some awareness of the potential for innovation and entrepreneurship, it is not being fully harnessed due to curriculum limitations. These findings align with those of Yusuf et al. (2024), who found that entrepreneurship education enables physics teachers to develop skills in identifying business opportunities, managing risks effectively, and mitigating economic challenges. Furthermore, Udoh and Okonkwo (2017) reported that the entrepreneurship content in the new curriculum is taught effectively by teachers, which significantly influences students' acquisition of entrepreneurship skills. The outcome also underscores that, when undergraduates in Imo State perceive thermodynamics principles as applicable, they can generate new solutions, create employment, and stimulate economic growth in areas such as renewable energy, manufacturing, and engineering (Mikielewicz & Mikielewicz, 2024).

It was also found that the perceived level of application of optics principles for job creation is low and not significantly greater than the criterion among undergraduates in tertiary institutions in Imo State. This low perceived rate indicates that although some students report using optics in innovative contexts, there is substantial room for growth through targeted interventions. This observation implies that with specialised guidance, including practical training and industry collaborations, undergraduates' perceived ability to innovate and generate employment in optics-related fields can be enhanced. The findings are consistent with Adeyemo et al. (2024), who found that the principles of optics have strongly influenced business ventures in Nigeria, stimulating innovation, economic development, and employment in fields such as telecommunications, health care, and manufacturing, and creating new industries and opportunities. Similarly, Ojo et al. (2023) observed that the principles of optics have been widely used in the Nigerian economy, with the country evolving and developing in the telecommunications, healthcare, manufacturing, renewable energy, and defence sectors, creating employment opportunities and attracting investments (Jeong et al., 2023).

Conclusion

This paper found that the perceived application of thermodynamics and optics concepts for job creation among undergraduates at tertiary institutions in Imo State is low and not significantly greater than

criterion levels, indicating potential but underutilised opportunities in physics education to foster entrepreneurship. Although some students perceive these principles as applicable to employment opportunities, the overall low level suggests room for improvement. The results underscore the importance of applied training, industry partnerships, and entrepreneurship development courses in improving students' perceived skills and unlocking their potential. There is a need to enhance the perceived use of physics principles in job creation in Imo State to achieve economic growth and development, aligning with national STEM-education reforms in Nigeria's National Policy on Education (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2013). The findings of the study can provide a foundation for stakeholders to formulate specific interventions to facilitate entrepreneurship and innovation among undergraduates. In this way, the tertiary institutions in Imo State can better prepare students with the perceived ability to generate employment and contribute to the state's economic growth.

Recommendations

Based on the research results, the researchers came to the following recommendations:

1. Imo State tertiary institutions must incorporate industry-related projects, practical training, and entrepreneurship development programmes that focus on applications of thermodynamics (e.g., project-based learning on energy-efficient designs) to equip students with sought-after skills and increase their employment opportunities.
2. The administrators of tertiary institutions in Imo State should foster industry partnerships and other hands-on training opportunities in fields related to optics (e.g., innovation challenges in photonics and medical imaging) to improve students' perceived skills and unlock their entrepreneurial potential for job creation.
3. Policymakers should integrate physics entrepreneurship into national STEM curricula, including industry collaborations for internships and funding for student-led ventures in thermodynamics and optics.

References

- Aboobaker, N., & Renjini, D. (2020). Human capital and entrepreneurial intentions: Do entrepreneurship education and training provided by universities add value? *On the Horizon*, 28(2), 73–90
- Adenutsi, D. (2023). Entrepreneurship, job creation, income empowerment and poverty reduction in low-income economies. *Theoretical Economics Letters*, 13, 1579–1598.
- Adeyemo, S. A., Babajide, V. F. T., & Onoyake, E. A. (2024). Impact of principles of optics on the economy of Nigeria. *International Journal of Advanced Studies in Engineering and Scientific Inventions*, 5(1), 171–182.
- Alasi, K. T., Eke, K. A., Baruwa, A., Mesele-Arokoyo, A., & Rasheed, A. A. (2015). Entrepreneurship and career development potentials for Nigerian physicists. *Science Journal of Business and Management*, 3(5–1), 55–59.
- Anekwe, R. I., Ndubuisi-Okolo, P., & Attah, E. Y. (2018). Effect of entrepreneurship development on poverty alleviation in Nigeria. *IOSR Journal of Business and Management*, 20(2), 80–87.
- Bao, L., & Cao, Y. (2019). Physics education research for 21st-century learning. *Active Learning in Higher Education*, 20(3), 201–209.
- Bawan, A. M., Kamgba, A. F., & Obi, D. O. (2024). Refocusing the teaching of physics for the technological development of Nigeria. *British Journal of Education, Learning and Development Psychology*, 7(3), 14–20.
- Born, M., & Wolf, E. (1999). *Principles of optics: Electromagnetic theory of propagation, interference and diffraction of light*. Cambridge University Press.
- Dirisu, G. B. (2020). Physicist entrepreneurial development: Ascertaining students' level of skills acquisition, readiness and implications for national development. *The Colloquium*, 8(1), 140–151.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria. (2013). *National policy on education (4th ed.)*. Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council.
- Găbureanu, S., & Tripon, C. (2020). Critical thinking in STEM learning. In *eLearning and Software for Education Conference* (pp. 1–7).
- International Finance Corporation. (2025). *Nigeria country private sector diagnostic*. International Finance Corporation.
- Jeong, Y. U., et al. (2023). Building an optics and photonics research ecosystem in South Korea: Collaborative innovation between academia and industry. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 120(49), e2314995120.
- Kontogeorgis, G. M., et al. (2021). Industrial requirements for thermodynamic and transport properties: 2020. *Industrial & Engineering Chemistry Research*, 60(13), 4987–5013.
- Maryanti, R., et al. (2023). How to improve critical thinking in physics learning? A systematic literature review. *Journal of Educational, Cultural and Psychological Studies*, 28, 161–187.
- Mikielewicz, D., & Mikielewicz, J. (2024). Influence of thermodynamics on the development of technology and science. *Archives of Thermodynamics*, 45(2), 51–61.
- Nasri, W., & Morched, S. (2023). Entrepreneurial intentions: The role of entrepreneurial self-efficacy in perspective of theory of planned behaviour. *Journal of Entrepreneurship Education*, 26(S3), 1–11.
- Ogunode, N. J., Edinoh, K., & Ibrahim, G. F. (2024). Tertiary education in Nigeria: Social problems/issues and possible solutions. Tunde Consult.

- Ogunleye, O. O. (n.d.). Entrepreneurship development using physics education. Academia.edu.
- Ojo, S. O., et al. (2023). Exploring the optical impact of information communication technology and economic growth on CO₂ emission in BRICS countries. *Optik*, 273, 170339.
- Osara, J. A. (2019). Thermodynamics of manufacturing processes—The workpiece and the machinery. *Inventions*, 4(2), 28.
- Onoyima, N. S., & Aka, C. P. (2023). Influence of tertiary education on empowerment and job creation through emerging technologies and innovations in Udenu Local Government Area (LGA) of Enugu State, Nigeria. *IAA Journal of Education*, 9(1), 56–65.
- Ridwan, A. I., Ayuba, J. S., & Shehu, A. (2025). Enhancing entrepreneurial skills through physics education in Nigerian colleges of education: A pathway to sustainable job creation. *Kontagora International Journal of Educational Research*, 2(3), 224–236.
- Stavropoulos, P., et al. (2024). Energy efficiency in the commercial sector: Thermodynamics fundamentals for the energy transition. *Energy Reports*, 11, 4601–4621.
- Udoh, A. O., & Okonkwo, P. (2017). The impact of the senior secondary school new physics curriculum on entrepreneurship skill acquisition among Nigeria physics students. *IDOSR Journal of Science and Technology*, 2(3), 12–21.
- Vogt, A. (2023). Innovative approaches for training precision optics technicians. In Proceedings of SPIE, 12723, 127231C.
- Yusuf, A. A., Akanbi, A. O., Ameen, K. S., Mohammed, R. E., & Kanu, A. C. (2024). Physics teachers' benefits of entrepreneurship skills acquisition. *Ilorin Journal of Education*, 45(1), 150–162